

Paper 20**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON REGULAR AND DISTANCE EDUCATION****Vidyalaxmi M. N. and Prajna Kumari**Srinivas University
Mangalore-575001**Abstract:**

Education is an integral part of human era. It helps in gaining knowledge and it changes the perspective of a person. We think logically and practically and then take decisions, as a result of which, we humans, are considered to be the most intelligent species on the planet. Education not only provides knowledge, but also contributes to the economic growth of a country and increases its stability. Since we all belong to different strata of the society, people go with a type of education which is suitable for them. According to the convenience of people, we have both regular and distance mode of education. In this paper, the Regular and Distance mode of education are compared based on their ability to provide quality and innovative post graduates in terms of quality, latest innovative curriculum, study materials, specialisations, programme duration, interactive sessions, flexibility, convenience, mentality of pupil and examination system and employability. Comparison is done by considering some of public and private universities who provide regular and distance post graduate education and their ability to add value to the programme with reference to quality, employability and convenience of pupil. Finally, merits and demerits of both regular and distance mode of education are identified and are listed under organisational, students, societal issues using focus group method.

Keywords: Regular education, Distance education, correspondence education, comparative study, education, interaction

1. INTRODUCTION:

Education is fundamental to human progress. It plays a major role in a development of an individual, a country, overall, a world. Every human needs to be educated. It makes him disciplined and social well being. Education system of India is similar to that of the Other South Asian countries. The components of our education system includes - regular program, correspondence program or distance program. Regular program consists of environment where students attend the class regularly and is being taught 6 to 7 hours a day, and then periodic exams are conducted by the college or university authority. The correspondence and distance education program means the same except for the fact that they differ in the methodology of teaching. A student pursuing correspondence program will be provided with the adequate study material and will be we asked to write the exams periodically. Here, no regular classes will be taken by any tutor to the students. Where as in the case of distance education 8 to 10 classes would be taken by the tutor online and the periodic examinations are conducted. Again, the classes here are not so regular like the regular education program. People pursuing correspondence or distance education program have an opportunity to work and learn simultaneously, that is they get paid and they need to pay.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Avani Trivedi , & Kalpana Gupte (2010) The article “**Quality Issues for Counselling in Open and Distance Learning in India**” is mainly intended to identify various aspects concerned with improving the quality of Counselling in Open and Distance Learning . The characteristics of distance education , the distance learner , the various mechanisms of learner support , the important role of the academic counselor in maintaining quality in distance learning are discussed and some measures are suggested based on TQM for maintaining the quality of counseling in distance learning with particular reference to IGNOU.[1]

Arun M. Sherry (2010) The author highlighted various benefits of distance mode of education and elaborates on how in a globalised society like that of India, the need for quality based higher education through distance learning mode is on constant rise. The author also examines various factors that are contributing to the growth of Management education through distance learning.[2]

Ashok Gaba and Shinja Koo (2007) The first part of the paper “**Research & Development of Distance Education in Asia: A Comparative Study between Korea National Open University, South Korea and Indira Gandhi National Open University, India**” compares the growth of distance education through analysis of the admission policies, enrolment trend, students support services and instructional system of both these institutions. The second part of the paper highlights the status, review and areas of research and research policies of these institutions. The findings of the paper are based on primary and secondary source of information.[3]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the rate of regular and correspondence education obtained by the students in India.
- To evaluate the reasons of the rejection of correspondence education in India.
- To find the appropriate measures on how to equalize correspondence education with regular education.
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4. METHODOLOGY:

The study on the above said objectives are based on secondary data. The conclusions drawn include details from authentic sources. This project consists of graphical representations and tables obtained from secondary data. Apart from this, expert in the area were consulted to arrive at a conclusion.

5. ANALYSIS:

According to the survey conducted during the year 2016 - 17 , by All India survey for higher education AISHE, 2,02,71,304 students have enrolled themselves under the regular education program, out of which approximately 23 lakhs students are pursuing post graduation program and 1,23,712 students pursuing PhD program. About 35,81,562 students have enrolled under distance education out of which 11,74,913 students have enrolled themselves in post graduation studies. In this analysis, the comparative study is done only for the post graduate programs of both regular and correspondence programs.

Table 01 – Enrolment of PG and UG in Regular mode of Education from 2012-2017.

ENROLMENT OF PG AND UG IN REGULAR MODE OF EDUCATION						
PROGRAMME		2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
UG	BA	7898579	9099473	9860520	9651891	9527060
	BSC	2947052	3579526	4299538	4618172	4978564
	BCOM	2810308	3117265	3381111	3422312	3484301
PG	MA	662839	674447	767027	878677	865410
	MBA	392587	392937	409432	416365	416490
	M.COM	179813	193373	222709	271266	275695
	M.SC	414316	431723	481330	519159	562896
	M.TECH	209720	260370	289311	257361	160888

Table 02 - Enrolment of PG and UG in Distance mode of Education from 2012- 2017

ENROLMENT OF PG AND UG IN DISTANCE MODE OF EDUCATION						
PROGRAMME		2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
UG	BA	1360044	1435302	1380114	1672872	1709590
	BSC	172442	272898	283185	201265	243606
	BCOM	372801	408957	460644	453274	507441
PG	MA	597170	729028	700338	652216	708599
	MBA	178742	165260	148895	132929	127275
	M.COM	86467	148419	147253	149447	171101
	M.SC	118150	125970	108962	96367	113938
	M.TECH	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 01 – Comparison of Regular and Distance education for the year 2016 -17

From the above data it is clear that highest number of students prefer Regular education over Distance mode of education.

According to the present scenario, **A student with PG degree under any Open Universities are not preferred over the one with the same PG degree under regular University for**

teaching programs in both Government and private sector. So it is obvious that a student with the degree under Open University cannot become a teacher. Why is it so?

There are multiple reasons for this out of which some are being mentioned. These reasons are purely based on secondary data collected.

- It is assumed that students who have pursued their education under the correspondence program are introvert, they are thought to be less interactive as there are no interactive classes taken for them, which, makes them unable to teach.
- It is also presumed that these students lack practical knowledge when compared to other students who do their degree and the regular program.
- Most of them feel that students under correspondence program study only during exams and nearly attend any classes unlike the regular batch students who attend the class everyday and write their exams.

Validating the above said reasons, each one could be justified. As it is said, that a book cannot be judged by its cover, similarly, a person cannot be judged by his certificate. Just because a person has acquired education under correspondence program, it doesn't mean that he is an introvert. It is not always true that they lack practical knowledge and they are unable to teach. It depends from one person to another. And yes, every individual has a different capacity of gaining knowledge. It is not necessary that all the students under correspondence education need to study a day before and write the exams. This could be done by a student who has the capacity to cover the entire syllabus at a stretch irrespective of him or her studying in regular or correspondence program.

6. DISCUSSION:

Basically there are three types of education systems in India - regular education, distance education and correspondence education. All the three systems have similar materials for a student to study on a particular course but they differ in the methodology involved in learning.

Fig 02 –Different types Education systems.

In India, there are 903 regular universities, out of which, 15 Open Universities are established so far. The following table represent detailed distribution of the universities across India.

Table 03- Types and number of universities during 2017-18

Types of Universities	Number of universities in 2017 -18
Central Open University	1
Central University	45
Deemed Government University	33
Institution under state legislature act	5
Institution of National Importance	101
Deemed private University	80
State Private University	262
State Open University	14
State Public University	351
State Private Open University	1
Deemed University Government Aided	10
TOTAL	903

- ❖ **Central Open University:** Central universities or union universities in India is a public distance learning university established by an Act of Parliament. They are under the purview of the Department of Higher Education in the Union Human Resource Development Ministry.
- ❖ **Central University:** Central universities or union universities in India is a public learning university (distance / & regular) established by an Act of Parliament. They are under the purview of the Department of Higher Education in the Union Human Resource Development Ministry.
- ❖ **Deemed Government University :** As explained by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), "An Institution of Higher Education, other than universities, working at a very high standard in specific area of study, can be declared by the Central Government on the advice of the University Grants Commission (UGC), as an Institution 'Deemed-to-be-university'.[4]
- ❖ **Institution under state legislature act:** these contain institutions that are developed and run under state legislature act.
- ❖ **Institution of national importance:** it is a Public Higher Education institution which receives recognition and funding from the Government of India.
- ❖ **Deemed private University:** these universities are run under university grant commission and are approved as Deemed to be university.
- ❖ **State private University:** it is a private University which is run under the state government.
- ❖ **State Open University:** it is a University that runs distance education and the state government.
- ❖ **State public University:** it is the university e which is run by the state government and is of the public which is usually funded by national or sub-national government. In India, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) , stands to be the largest University to provide distance education in the world, which is a state public University.

- ❖ **State private Open University:** it is a private University that provides distance education and is run by the state government.
- ❖ **Deemed university government aided:** it is a deemed university that is funded or aided by government.

As it is known every coin has two sides, our education programmes has both pros and cons.

Merits of regular education program include:

- ❖ Interaction - a classroom environment provides a better platform for one to share his opinion and to gain knowledge. A Regular programs makes one express his opinion and usually creates extroverts. Activities like seminars presentations discussions helps one to build his personality and makes them both physically and mentally strong and stable. It adds on to one's social behaviour.
- ❖ Clarification - it is easier for a pupil to clarify and clear his doubts then and there II in the classroom.
- ❖ Notes - on the regular basis of Pupil make sure that is notes is up to date.
- ❖ Schools for disabled - it is a great convenience for the special abled people. Disabled people require assistance which is provided by the regular schooling system.
- ❖ Social interaction. - Regular schooling helps one to gain many friends hence improving ones social interaction.

Demerits of regular education include-

- ❖ Providing education has become am your business. Our education system creates a lot of Machines but not what the creators. Students only depend on textbook and tutors for knowledge and do not approach themselves to study anything extra. This brings them a title of a perfect "bookworms".
- ❖ The selection process - the system of reservation has created quite a blunder in the regular education system. Reserved candidates have very low cut off, very low fee a great priorities because of which The talented individuals are left out.
- ❖ Syllabus - the regular education system consists of was syllabus which needs to be covered at a certain period of time. Hence, the teachers always in to cover the syllabus and rarely share things which are of great general knowledge.
- ❖ Homework: every Pupil in the regular education system is supposed to complete the homework which creates the burden in a pupil. These homework consists of writing pages and pages and nearly gaining knowledge. The result of this Bean we stop time burden to Pupil both physically and mentally and hatred towards this education system.
- ❖ Product of the education- it is said that India produces mostly service based students and not product based as we have lots of Service Company where as low levels of product based companies. We always lack in producing innovative products.
- ❖ Mentality of pupil towards the education system - students under regular education program nowadays have a mentality of just passing the University exams. The aim of this generation is to score good in the exams irrespective of whether he or she against the knowledge or not. Scores do not tell whether a person is knowledgeable or not.

Merits of Distance Education are:

- ❖ Saves time and money: Due to absence of regular class, time of the pupil is saved. Also, the fee for distance education is quite less as when compared to regular education.
- ❖ Preference of time for study: a student can easily fit into his time and study accordingly.

- ❖ Study from anywhere: A student can study from any place, according to his comfort zone.
- ❖ Flexible: Distance education offers flexibility than any other education system.

Demerits of Distance education includes:

- ❖ Feeling Isolated: Since distance education doesn't involve classroom environment, the pupil is readily to feel isolated.
- ❖ Lack of Oral communication Skills: absence of classroom environment and discussions has lead to a decrease in the oral communication skill.
- ❖ Need to have access to technology: To stay updated, a student needs to have a continuous access to internet and other technology.
- ❖ Doubts are not cleared immediately: Due to lack of interaction based classes, doubts of a pupil remain for a longer time.

7. SUGGESTIONS:

Evaluating all of the above gives rise to a question,- what could be done about to solve this? What could be the measures taken so as to equate regular program to correspondence program? Here are some of them. Again, these measures are truly based on the secondary data collected.

- In a country like India, nothing works without implementing the law. So, a suitable law must be implemented that equal opportunity must be given to the people who pursue their studies under the correspondence program. Only formulating law is not enough, it should be implemented effectively
- Both the mode of education must be given equal weightage by the universities and other organizations.
- Candidates must be selected for the particular designation based on his/her skills and knowledge rather than the mode of education.

8. CONCLUSION:

So far, we have seen how each education system has brought a great impact on us. Either way, both have their own merits and demerits. According to their convenience and needs, each prefers one of the systems. As witnessed through various studies, institution providing distance education programme also has comparable number of students pursuing their studies. Each mode of education has its own effectiveness which depends on mentality of the people and how they perceive it. Awareness about the qualities of each mode of education must be conducted so that society will give equal chance to both by analysing it.

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